

Gender Differences And Relationship Between Group Identification And Conflict Resolution Among University Students

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Abstract— This research study has investigated the “Gender Differences in and Relationship between Group Identity and Conflict Resolution among University Students”. This research was based on cross sectional survey research design. The convenience sample was used by including 100 Students (50 male and 50 female) studying at University of Gujrat. The study variables were measured using Group Identification scale proposed by Cameron (2004) and Conflict Resolution scale by Springer (1992). The main objectives of this study were to measure the Group Identification, conflict Resolution and gender differences among University students. And it was hypothesized that higher the Group Identification Lower the Conflict and there will be negative relationship between group Identification and Conflict Resolution. Data was analyzed with statistical package for social sciences (SPSS-16 version). Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to find out the relationship between group Identification and Conflict Resolution. The t-test was computed to find out the gender differences. The result findings of the study supported that people with the sense of Group Identification have less indulge in Conflict related situation and Gender differences exist among the respondents.

Keywords— Gender Difference, Group Identity, Conflict Resolution.

I. INTRODUCTION

Group Identification Group is defined as two or more people who interact with each other, share similar characteristics and have a sense of unity. Group can be define as a number of individuals interacting with each other in term of common motives and goals, roles, established status relationships [1].

An in-group is a social category or group with which you identify strongly. An out-group, conversely, is a social category or group with which you do not identify [1].

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Group identification is indeed multidimensional. The most comprehensive attempt to examine this empirically [2] showed that there are several aspects to identity: attraction to the group, interdependency (a sense that the group's fate is one's own), depersonalization (the sense that one is absorbed in the group so that members are more or less interchangeable), and inter-group context (a tendency to see one's own group identity in contrast to other groups). We are concerned with our social image or how other people see us; some more than others, but very few people see no difference in their behavior. When alone, we tend to be more relaxed, less concerned with the outward expression of our behavior, and are basically 'ourselves' [3].

There are always two kind of things which can happen in a group decision making process, either the group agree on all the major terms, or there is great dissent and that splits the group. If the group agree on most of the issues, they tend to reject the dissent because harmony in the group should be anticipated outcome [3].

Group polarization is defined as tendency of a group to take extreme positions. In this situation, the group becomes so focused and passionate about the decision that an internal fuel is created. Another important phenomenon which is normally created in group is named as Social Loafing. It is defined as, the group size becomes bigger, the individual contribution reduces disproportionately to the size of the group [3]. This occurs due to the diffusion of responsibility as the size of the group increases. The phenomenon is also an unfortunate reality which is evident and observed quite often in groups and in larger cities. It has been observed the internal push to help a person who actually need help goes down as the group size gets bigger. People becomes to be followers and only perform if they see another individual is getting involved [3].

Conflict resolution is defined as a way for both the parties to find a suitable and peaceful solution to a disagreement among them. This disagreement can be financial, emotional or personal. Groups in conflict normally produce negative stereotypes of each other oversimplified, rigid, wrong and derogatory beliefs about the properties of the other group that are applied indiscriminately to all the individual members of the group. All these things come partly through the process of group categoration, which create the differences and homogeneity out of the group [4].

Conflict is basically a process that normally happens in layers. The first layer of the conflict is always . The other following layers includes are differences of values and point of view, and inter-personal differences. The conflict may exist anywhere. The way of thinking of two persons is always different. Hence they can have individual differences and these differences may occur because of different values and otherwise. These differences may lead to conflict. Conflict is normal in life. Individuals, groups and organizations have unlimited needs but limited resources. It must be perceived by all parties. In interpersonal relation, perception is the most important than reality. One party may be perceiving or performing, the other party may be don't like or want. There should be independence in interaction. Conflict occurs when some misconception occurs [5]. Normally, behavior is learnt in families. In some families. Conflict and confrontation is part of communication style and in others conflict always remain hidden. Behaviors are also learnt by following role models. People having high status positions normally feel free to jump into conflict and are less likely to avoid confrontation. Some groups encourage conflict whereas others have written rules of conflict to avoid. Males are normally encouraged to be more confrontational than females [6].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Many researchers have conducted research across the world, on Group Identity and Conflict Resolution and also on the relationship between these two. The studies have also tried to analyze the various aspects/factors associated with both Group Identity and Conflict Resolution. The following presented are some of the studies that try to understand the dynamics of Group Identity and Conflict Resolution.

Jehn and Mannix (2001). Conducted a research on "The Dynamic Nature of Conflict: A Longitudinal Study of Intergroup Conflict and Group Performance". The results of this study indicated that performance of bigger group I associated with a pattern of conflict. The teams performing well were characterized by low but increasing level of conflict, less relationship conflict, with rise near the deadlines of project and moderate levels of task conflict at midpoint of group interaction. The team members with this ideal conflict profile had almost same pre-established value systems, high level of respect and trust and most importantly open discussion norms around conflict at the middle stages of their interactions [7].

Paul S. et. al. (2004) has conducted a study on the topic "Impact of heterogeneity and collaborative conflict management style on the performance of synchronous global virtual teams". This study identified the relationship that may exist among heterogeneity of the virtual teams, their conflict management methods, and their performance results. This paper basically reported the results of lab experiment in which heterogeneous and homogeneous teams having subjects from India and USA. A web-based group decision system was used by the team members that provided them the chance to discuss task options, critique suggestions, and vote on the results. The results of data analysis showed that collaborative conflict

management style had a positive impact satisfaction with decision making process, perceived decision making process and decision quality and perceived anticipation of the virtual teams. There was a weak evidence that links heterogeneity of a group to its conflict management style [8].

Holt and Devore (2005) conducted a research on the topic of "Culture, gender, organizational role, and styles of conflict resolution: A meta-analysis". The data consisted of 123 paired comparisons with 36 empirical studies. The result indicated individual culture chose forcing more than collective culture on conflict style. Collectivistic cultures choose the style of withdraw, compromise and problem solving more than the individualistic cultures. Females are more likely to endorse the use of compromising than the males members whereas males are more likely to choose a forcing style with their supervisors [9].

Sheryl D, et al. (2005) conducted a research on the topic "A gender-based categorization for conflict resolution". The main objective of this study was to investigate the assumptions that may exist regarding the relationship among gender and conflict resolution. The main intent of this study was to understand and compare the conflict resolution strategies of males and females majoring in information system (IS) to find whether a gender-based difference exist. The Thomas-Kilmann Conflict Mode Instrument was utilized to assess the conflict resolution styles of 163 age (18-22) students enrolled in undergraduate IS courses at a large Midwestern university. Both ANOVA and t-test analyses were utilized to investigate the relationship between gender and conflict resolution style. Results of the study indicate that women are more likely to utilize a collaborative conflict resolution style and men are more likely to avoid conflict. The study also suggests that women may possess more effective conflict resolution attributes than their male counterparts [10].

Boros, S et.al. (2009) Conducted a study on the topic Struggles for cooperation: conflict resolution strategies in multicultural groups. The basic purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of group composition in cultural values on conflict management styles in groups. A field study was designed using data from 125 groups. The results indicated that in a groups where members feel they are equal and connected, the cooperation is better, and contending and avoiding conflict management styles are less required. When people view themselves as unequal and independent, the avoiding style of conflict management is more frequently needed. Within a group similarity leads to more cooperation and less avoidant conflict management strategies as well as less third party interventions. High group variety in views of being unequal, but interconnected, as well as in the views of being equal but independent, leads to more cooperative conflict resolution strategy. The results showed that small and consistent within-group differences in cultural values are beneficial for cooperative strategies [11].

Johnson, D W. Johnson, R T. (2012). Carried out a research on the topic "Conflict Resolution and Peer Mediation

Programs in Elementary and Secondary Schools: A Review of the Research". This research explained the concern about violence in schools has been increasing, and, correspondingly, conflict resolution and peer mediation training programs have been proliferating. These programs have been developed by researchers in the field of conflict resolution, advocates of non-violence, anti-nuclear-war activists, and members of the legal profession. The results mentioned that conflicts among students do occur frequently in schools. The untrained students by and large use conflict strategies that create destructive outcomes by ignoring the importance of their ongoing relationships. The conflict resolution and peer mediation programs do seem to be more effective in teaching students integrative negotiation and mediation procedures. After training, students tend to use these conflict strategies, which normally leads to better outcomes and students success in resolving their conflicts constructively tends to result in reducing the numbers of student to student conflicts [12].

III. METHODOLOGY

The present study was Correlational. A cross sectional survey research design was used to collect the data from respondents. The target population of the current study was comprised of 100 university students of BS (HONS) and MS, from the faculty of Social Sciences departments. In the faculty of social sciences department, the data was collected from Psychology, Sociology and Economics departments from Gujrat University. Convenience sampling technique was used for data collection from the respondents. In the present study two standardized questionnaire were used to measure the Group Identity and Conflict Resolution among university students. For measuring the Group Identity among students "Group Identification Scale (Cameron, 2004)" was used. For measuring the Conflict Resolution (Phillips & Springer, 1992) was used. Group Identification scale is 12-item instrument that is designed to identify and measure group identification that an individual perceive in their own group. The instrument contained three dimensions Centrality, In Group Affect, In Group Ties, Each dimension contains 4 items. All items were responded to on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly Agree). Fifty percent of the items on the scale required reverse scoring. The second scale was Conflict Resolution Scale is 12-items instrument that is designed to identify and measure of one's ability to manage and resolve conflict in a positive way. The two conflict resolution skills emphasized are self-control and cooperation. Two subscales and each subscale have six items. Responses are scored as follows: YES! = 4, yes= 3, no= 2 and NO! = 1. This format requires explanation to respondents before the scale is administered. Reverse coding is necessary. All six items on the self- control scale are reverse coded. Responses are then summed to create a final score. High scores then reflect more cooperation and self-control. In addition, the demographic sheet was used to collect the demographic data from the respondents in term of their Name, Age, Gender, semester, department etc.

IV. PROCEDURE

The purpose and objectives of the study were explained to all respondents. Before the administration of the scale the instructions were given to the respondents and asked them to read each statement carefully and select suitable option according to their own opinion. All respondents were assured that their responses would keep confidential. After the data collection, the data analysis was made by using SPSS-16 (Statistical Package for social sciences). Descriptive statistical analysis was conducted to compute Mean and Standard Deviation of variables and values of the respondents on each dimension of the scale. The Person Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was employed to find out the Gender differences in and relationship between Group Identity and Conflict Resolution among university students.

V. RESULTS

Frequency (f) and Percentage (%) values of the characteristics of Demographic Variables were computed in Table I. T-test of Group Identification and Conflict Resolution Scale (N=100) was computed in Table II. Pearson Product Moment Correlation and independent sample t-test were applied on the scores of Group Identification scale and Conflict Resolution scale.

TABLE I FREQUENCY AND PERCENTAGE VALUES OF CHARACTERISTICS OF DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

Variable	Range	F	(%)
Age	19-21	57	57.0
	22-24	43	43.0
Gender	Male	52	52.0
	Female	48	48.0
Semester	BS(Hons)	47	47.0
	MS	53	53.0
Department	Psychology	31	31.0
	Sociology	35	35.0
	Economics	34	34.0

The above table shows the demographic variables including Age ranging from 19 to 24 with (57.0 & % 43.0%), Gender including Male (52%) and Female (48%), Semester including BS (Hons) (47.0%) and MS (53.0%), Department including Psychology (31%), Sociology (35%), Economics (34%).

TABLE II T-TEST GROUP IDENTIFICATION AND CONFLICT RESOLUTION SCALE (N=100)

	M	SD	t	p	LL	UP
Total Group Identity	-	-	-	-	-	-
Male	35.6	8.39	-2.30	.023	-7.6	-5
Female	39.7	9.3	-	-	-	-
Total Conflict Resolution	-	-	-	-	-	-
Male	29.8	3.61	3.32	.001	1.00	3.9
Female	27.3	3.8	-	-	-	-

Table shows that the mean value of (t=-2.3) and (p=.023) <.05 which shows that there is a significant difference between Male and Female on Group Identification scale. On the other hand the results of the Conflict Resolution Scale shows the mean value (t=3.32) and (p=.001) <.05 which shows significant difference between male and female resolve there conflicts.

TABLE III PERSON PRODUCT MOMENT CORRELATION COEFFICIENT BETWEEN GROUP IDENTITY AND CONFLICT RESOLUTION (N=100)

Measures	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Mean	SD
Total Group Identity	-	-						37.6	9.06
		.232*							
Total Conflict Resolution	-	-	-					28.6	3.92
			.263*						
Centrality	-	-	-	-				11.0	4.81
				.339*					
In-group Affect	-	-	-	-	.013			13.2	3.82
In-group ties	-	-	-	-	-	.003		13.2	4.28
Self-Control	-	-	-	-	-	-	.108	10.9	2.80
Cooperation	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	17.6	3.06

Note:*.Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

As the above Table III shows that there is significant Negative correlation between total Group Identity and Conflict Resolution (-.232*), significant negative correlation between Conflict Resolution and Centrality (-.263**), significant correlation between Centrality and In-group Affect (.339**), correlation between In-group Affect and In-group Ties (.013), negative Correlation between In-group Ties and Self Control (-.033), negative Correlation between Self Control and Cooperation (-.108).

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aimed to investigate the “Gender differences in and relationship between Group Identification and Conflict Resolution among University Students. Findings of the study supported the hypothesis that higher the group identification lowers the conflict among the member of the group. And the study depict that there was a negative correlation between group identification and conflict resolution among the respondents. And both variables are negatively correlated with each other’s and gender differences were existed among the respondents.

The first objective of the study was to measure the Group Identification among University Students. The previous result indicated that Group Identity extends or redirects the cognitive and motivational processes that produce positive feelings toward in-group members to former out-group members. They equal status between the memberships, cooperative interdependence, opportunity for self-revealing interactions and egalitarian norms, successfully reduce bias (Gaertner S, L. et al, 1996) [13].

The second objective of the study was to measure the conflict Resolution among University Students. The result of the research show that the students with the most positive perception of the schoolmates and university students are more willing to adopt constructive conflict management strategies (Giulia, Vincenza, Davide, 2010) [14].

The third objective is to find out the Gender differences among University Students. The previous study indicated that there were differences in the male’s way that subordinates evaluated male and female supervisors who used similar styles. It also indicate that women are more likely to utilize a collaborative conflict resolution style and men are more likely to avoid conflict Dominating was more negatively related, and obliging more positively related, to subordinates' perceptions of effectiveness for women than for men (Karen, Galen, Carol, 1993) [15].

The fourth objective of the study is to find out the relationship between Group identification and Conflict Resolution among University students. The result presents in Table III showed that negative correlation between Group Identity and Conflict Resolution. Centrality, In-group Affect, In-group-ties are the dimensions of Group Identity that were positively correlated with cooperation and self-control dimension of Conflict Resolution was negatively associated with In-group-ties.

Findings of the study supported the hypotheses that higher the group identification lowers the conflict among the member of a group. And the study depict that there was a negative correlation between group identification and conflict resolution among the respondents. And both variables are negatively correlated with each other's and gender differences were existed among the respondents.

VII. RECOMMENDATIONS AND LIMITATIONS

Although the findings of the present study showed significant results, but it may have some limitations and drawbacks in it.

- The current study was conducted only on the faculties of social sciences, University of Gujrat, Hafiz Hayat Campus. The students from other department faculties were not included in the sample. So this reason could also limit the generalizability of the results.
- Since the self-report measures were used to collect the data, so there is the possibility that the respondents might hide their true responses.
- Both scales were administered in English which may have effect on respondent's level of understandings.

On the basis of the above limitations there are some suggestions that are given below;

- The present study in this area will provide help to those who are interested in conducting research in future.

As it mention earlier that faculties of other sciences (expectsocial sciences) were not included. So it is suggested that other faculties must include in future research, so that the results would be generalized

VIII. CONCLUSION

The present study was Correlational study conducted to find out the Gender differences in and relationship between Group Identification and Conflict Resolution among university students. There was significantly negative correlation between these two variables. As higher the group identification leads toward lower the conflict among the respondents of Gujrat University. Gender differences were existing among the respondents of Gujrat University.

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